

ПСИХОЛОГІЧНИЙ СТАН МЕДИЧНИЙ ПРАЦІВНИКІВ ПІД ЧАС ПАНДЕМІЇ COVID-19: МЕТА-АНАЛІЗ

THE PSYCHOLOGICAL STATE OF HEALTHCARE WORKERS DURING THE PANDEMIC OF COVID-19: META-ANALYSIS

О.В. Мац¹, Д.І. Бойко²

O.V. Mats¹, D.I. Boiko²

ORCID¹: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7489-5711>

ORCID²: orcid.org/0000-0001-7336-0822

Полтавський державний медичний університет
Кафедра психіатрії, наркології та медичної психології
м. Полтава, Україна

Poltava State Medical University
Department of Psychiatry, Narcology and Medical Psychology
Poltava, Ukraine
e-mail: bojko998@gmail.com

Introduction. The psychological state is an important component of human life, so any impact on it is extremely important. Today, a pressing question arises, which includes the need to study the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the psycho-emotional state of healthcare workers, as they are the first line between the dangerous virus and the health of patients. Every day, healthcare workers are faced with additional layers of responsibility that exacerbate mental and physical exhaustion, which confirms the view of the threat to the functioning of a holistic health care system in a pandemic of COVID-19.

Objective: To evaluate the data on the psychological state of medical workers in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic in comparison with specialists in non-medical specialties.

Materials and methods. We conducted a systematic search in the database PubMed and Cochrane Library until December 27, 2021 articles in English. We used the following search strategy: (((COVID-19) OR (SARS_COV-2)) AND (((mental health) OR (stress)) OR (anxiety)) OR (depression))) AND (((nurse) OR (physician)) OR (doctor)) OR (healthcare worker)). The meta-analysis included only the results of observational studies published in English, which examined the levels of anxiety, depression, and stress on the DASS-21 scale of medical and non-medical workers, and did not risk systematic error according to the Cochrane Regulation on writing systematic reviews of interventions. Heterogeneity was assessed using I^2 statistics. The meta-analysis was performed using the fixed effects method using Review Manager 5.

Results. The meta-analysis included 2 studies with a total number of 912 respondents who met the required criteria. According to the meta-analysis, it was found that in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, healthcare workers have increased stress levels compared to non-medical specialties by almost 1.5 times (OR = 1.47, 95%CI 1.02-2.12, $p=0.040$). The level of anxiety in healthcare workers compared to specialists in other fields and specialties increased by 2 times in a pandemic (OR =

2.07, 95%CI 1.45-2.96, $p < 0.001$). According to selected studies, the level of depression in health professionals did not differ significantly from those in other industries (OR = 1.02, 95%CI 0.69-1.50, $p = 0.920$).

Conclusions. Thus, healthcare workers are found to be more prone to stress and anxiety than those working in other industries in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. However, the small number of studies included should be taken into account due to the significant quality requirements of the selected analytical studies, which may lead to variability in results.